

RESEARCH DATA STRATEGY

**DELIVERING WUR DATA TO THE
WORLD**

WAGENINGEN
UNIVERSITY & RESEARCH

Summary of recommendations

1. **Digital Companions** – Researchers should deliver data and models in digital, actionable formats when users most need it.
2. **Distribute & Standardize** – Research data should be stored in domain-specific data repositories, and interfaces must be standardised.
3. **Empower Governance** – Make policies and legal frameworks actionable, so that they work to researchers' advantage instead of limiting them.
4. **Machine Actionable** – Enable researchers to create FAIR data: 'Findable Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable' as well as 'Fully AI Ready'.
5. **Registration & Classification** – Actively engage researchers on the importance of data registration & classification to protect data that matters most.
6. **Infrastructure Accessibility** – ensure that all data infrastructure is useable by all researchers, no matter their budget or experience; eliminating financial & administrative barriers and educating users.

● Data analysis

● Data processing

● Data creation

Data from and to the natural world

Digital companions

Distribute & standardise

Empower governance

Machine actionable

Accessible infrastructure

Data classification

Authors: Erik van den Bergh, Willem Jan Knibbe (Wageningen Data Competence Center)

Discussions and manuscript corrections: Lotte de Vos, Yannick van Gelder, Hans Vrolijk, Karin Andeweg, Roel Veerkamp, Ioannis Athanasiadis, Lonneke van der Geest, Jan Top, Frits van Evert, Harm Nijveen

Introduction

Wageningen University & Research (WUR) is a scientific research institute that aims to address global societal challenges in agriculture, nature, nutrition and health. The ever increasing possibilities for digital data collection and modelling enable exciting possibilities for new ways to solve these challenges. The natural world around us can be digitally captured through increasingly more detailed techniques and devices. Sensors placed in the gut are capable of generating millions of datapoints in a single day. Flying LIDAR techniques are capable of scanning thousands of trees per second in the rainforest. Aerial drones are able to scan hectares of acres every day. This deluge of data requires new methods and infrastructure to derive scientific insight, leading to questions on how to prepare for this new future. In this strategy, six strategic recommendations are made that will enable WUR to solve the questions of tomorrow with new and exciting science.

This document is the result of five 2½ hour sessions with representatives from each Science Group (kenniseenheid), equally divided between WU and WR. While the COVID-19 pandemic necessitated transferring these sessions from offline to online, numerous valuable insights were shared, discussed and captured. On top of that this strategy contains the enormous amount of insight that the Wageningen Data Competence Center (WDCC) has gathered for the past 3 years being a part of the WUR organisation. In this Research Data Strategy, current fundamental issues are addressed and solutions are recommended, divided into 6 areas: Data delivery, standardisation, governance, architecture, security and accessibility. Each chapter begins with the main recommendation to further enhance the position of WUR in these areas, ending with a summary of detailed, actionable recommendations.

Perhaps, it seems strange to write a *data* strategy. After all, data is merely a representation to measure the world around us and can only provide input to solve human scientific questions. However, management and delivery of data greatly affect the questions it can be used to answer. At a citizen level, the persistent availability of Wikipedia has changed our capacity to answer everyday questions from the moment they pop into our heads. At a scientific level, genetic data repositories such as the NCBI Sequence Read Archive have made large scale genetic comparison feasible for any scientist anywhere in the world at a moment's notice. While a wealth of information can easily be captured by machines, it is much harder to present it meaningfully to users with varying backgrounds, skill levels and questions. As the amount of data increases exponentially, newer methods are constantly required to provide insight into these collections. This Research Data Strategy therefore outlines what WUR should do to embrace and effectively use one of the most valuable results of its scientific excellence: research data.

Contact with 100's of researchers, students and specialists through each of the WDCC programme lines has resulted in a great body of knowledge on the state of data science & data management in WUR. This strategic document bundles this knowledge to provide an outlook towards the future and the challenges that we expect to face in the coming 3-5 years. With this strategy, WUR is able to apply and enhance new technological opportunities to further increase its scientific excellence.

Throughout this strategy, we will distinguish 3 different user groups that subdivide the WUR researcher population (see figure inset). The first and smallest group are the innovators. They know which technology works best for their research and actively develop new means to further enhance their research capabilities. While small, this group tends to have a dominant position in discussions on technology choice & policy. While this is appropriate due to their expertise, care must be taken to not let (unconscious) bias steer the research data strategy too much towards innovator domains. For example, while AI has a natural link to Robotics, AI techniques are just as applicable in the health & food domain.

The other two groups consist of developers and users. They are similar in the sense that they do not actively create new technology; they differ in their level of expertise of applying technology to their research practice. While developers have mastery of one or a few programming languages or platforms and actively use it in their analyses, users are bound to graphically oriented, mostly standard programs. Of course, no single researcher fits one of these categories in every aspect. But this model serves well to determine the right amount of effort that needs to be directed to various strategic goals.

It is important to note that data and digital technology should never be a goal in themselves. They are always a means by which human scientific goals are achieved. This also implies that the means need to work *for* humans and not *against* them. This has both practical and ethical consequences, which will be explained more in depth in the last chapter. While data driven methods are a means to an end, new means can offer new ends. At time of writing of this document, a team of computer scientists working with DeepMind AI technology claim to have solved the prediction of protein folding based purely on their amino acid sequence. Due to the immense number of possible interactions that can take place within an amino acid chain, this has been a 30 year standing problem in structural proteomics. How should WUR exploit this new tool? What groups will be able to apply this in their research, and what infrastructure will they need? These are the types of questions that must be answered to effectively explore the possibilities offered to us by new technology. This strategic document describes how WUR should use its most valuable asset – its scientific excellence – to answer these questions in the near future. It details how actively presented, FAIR data can facilitate answering questions of the future. The strategic goals are summarised in 6 recommendations, which form the main chapters of this document. In each chapter, present and future expectations are described as well as what WUR should do to best address what is next. The last chapter outlines ways to bring these recommendations into action. Taken together, the Research Data Strategy will

strengthen and expand the scientific and data driven excellence of WUR in all its research domains.

Digital Companion

Research data is of vital importance in exposing scientific results to WUR partners and society. While raw delivery of data is sometimes desirable, the appropriate scientific context to guide decision making based on this data is crucial to real life application. Right now, interpretation of data and guidance for decision making is largely provided by *human interface* means, i.e. scientific articles and reports. These provide information on the strengths and limitations of the data and make clear what they can and cannot be used for. However, information provided through text is static and must always be written with assumptions towards reader expertise and use case.

Using digital technology, results can be delivered differently. It becomes possible to continuously update data in real time up to the microsecond; allowing decisions to be made accurately even in rapidly changing environments. An extreme example of such a real time data delivery system is a digital twin, a virtual copy of a system that constantly is kept in sync with its sibling through continuous data flow. This allows an immediate and complete overview of the most complex systems for rapid decision making.

But because digital twins strive for completeness, they quickly become complex. Expertise is needed to accurately judge what the presented information means. Even for (groups of) experts such large amounts of information can be hard to interpret. Therefore data delivery can also be performed through a *digital companion*: an application that presents information in a way that is easy to interpret by a human.

ask-Valerie is a search engine based on dialogue that helps the user in formulating their question and in answering it in a useful way. Through annotation of documents based on ontological terms, it allows a user to see at one glance what the content of a document is.

This allows end users to translate scientific results to their own situation and provides a platform for educators and their community to reach more users in a practical way.

Well known examples of a digital companions are currently popular digital assistants: Siri (Apple), Alexa (Amazon) and the Google assistant. While their applications are limited and simplistic, they provide an example of the most fundamental human interface to complex data: language. Language is the most natural way for humans to exchange information and it is used as a medium by all people on earth. A digital companion therefore aims to provide information

through this medium, enhancing it with visual or auditory aids where necessary. It aims to break down large amounts of data into human interpretable chunks and presents them to the user in at the right moment, in the right form. This can be as an alert, e.g. to water crops when a certain soil moisture level has been reached, or in response to a question asking whether to buy 0%-fat, sweetened yoghurt or the full fat, sugar free variety.

Digital companions provide added (commercial) value to groups that currently deliver information through static means. Because of their real-time nature they also stimulate a more long term relation with end users to continuously provide access to information. This means subscription based commercial models become viable, but infrastructure to manage these types of payment must be available. Large technology companies such as IBM, Intel and Microsoft present edge computing infrastructures that enable decision making power in small portable devices; these solutions can provide the 'final mile' towards the end user. Collaboration to further apply these new technologies can provide fertile ground for public-private partnerships.

Because digitally stored data is not easily converted to time-based, human language information, a digital companion needs to be able to translate both to and from this medium. Natural language modelling is inescapable to provide this functionality. These models provide the last (and first) step towards the end user and can be used generically. However, converting data into decision support ready *information* requires ontological models that map domain knowledge onto real-time data. These ontologies and vocabularies must be filled by domain experts and must be refined based on user questions. While this is a time consuming process, the resulting semantic web provides long-term value for presenting results dynamically based on user need.

Digital companions increase value of WUR knowledge for the end user by delivering it where they need it, when they need it and with their context in mind. A challenge with this always-on delivery models is to provide reliable (virtual) infrastructure; current project-based financial structures hamper this because of their temporary nature. New financial ways to provide continuity in services are needed to make digital companions a reality.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Currently, the scientific article or report form the large majority of output for both publicly funded and contract research within WUR. Because technology now is an unmissable link of everyday life, it provides new opportunities to deliver WUR expertise to whoever needs it. This allows partners, customers and society to reap the benefits of the scientific expertise that WUR gathers; no matter their education, geographic location or spoken language. WUR should enable further research into optimal data translation models. It should also provide technological means, such as app frameworks, visualisation methods, links to popular software and natural language models to researchers in every domain to enable them to map their expertise to their data and create their own *digital companion*.

Summarising, WUR should:

- Provide infrastructure to create end user platforms, such as apps, web portals etc. coupled with consultancy on how to make these platforms work for the end user (UX design) and support these centrally.
- Research the semantic modelling of domain knowledge for data mapping in response to end user questions. This includes context sensitive mapping, taking into account user situation, preferred medium, up to date source data, etc.
- Provide payment infrastructure and explore new continuous financial models, to make always-on delivery platforms financially feasible for research groups.

Distribute & standardise

Data is more valuable when shared. Because of the worldwide distribution of scientific knowledge, collaboration between researchers, professionals and society is fundamental to modern science. This means that data must be able to travel and still be usable by every researcher. Online and cloud technology fulfil a key role in this exchange. However, they are hampered by physical and technological limitations, especially when transferring large or complex datasets. In life sciences analyses tend to be data heavy which means computation must be *high throughput*. This contrasts with a lot of current academic computational infrastructure which is usually built for *high performance*, i.e. suited for computationally heavy but data-light computation. Networking infrastructure between compute clusters is therefore usually not built to move large datasets¹ around the globe. In life sciences we must therefore adopt a *compute-to-data* model, in which data remains where it is and (virtual) compute infrastructure is available around it to perform analysis. Another option is streaming data from a central repository, but this usually requires significant adaptations in the analysis software to deal with non-classical file structures. To enable data to remain in place and allow computational methods to travel, data and workflows must be standardised.

The Farm Data Train project aims to connect agricultural data to make them more usable.

It outlines a model of computational 'trains' that visit data 'stations'. The stations present their data using standardised interfaces, allowing various types of trains to derive the information they need in an automated fashion. Data are secured by a robust authentication and authorisation system that safeguards specific station requirements.

Standardisation of data is a complex topic. The main tension is created by specificity for a certain purpose versus general exchangeability. With scientific data especially, data that is fit for purpose must be complex due to the precise and specialistic nature of research. This, combined with the innovative character of scientific investigation that implies constantly changing parameters and structure makes data standardisation a tough nut to crack. However, while small innovative research

data is hard to standardise, established, large scale data collections are well suited for producing stable structured data. Genomic sequencing analyses, satellite imagery, and consumer / patient questionnaires are examples from the WUR domain that many groups deal with and that are produced in bulk according to community standards. At a higher level, most data can be categorised using general metadata schemas such as Dublin core, for archival purposes. While they describe the data content only

¹ "Large datasets" in this case mean datasets that require significant amounts of time (>3 hours) to transfer over the appropriate network

superficially, these metadata can be applied to any dataset regardless of origin making it a universal exchange format.

The dichotomy of standardised, exchangeable data versus specific, intraoperable data requires an architecture that can handle both. Data should be able to be stored and represented in its most detailed form and should at the same time be available represented in canonical, less detailed schemas to facilitate

exchange. Because detailed storage and representation of data should be a community led process, it makes sense to embrace the distributed nature of community repositories. Virtually all disciplines, from humanities to mathematics have specialised repositories where data is stored according to the metadata that is most useful to that community. Community led repositories are not only of high quality, but they also form major hubs of trust. They also lead expansion of metadata standards as scientific insight progresses. It is impossible to replace these communal, scattered repositories by a single centralised solution; this solution could never approach the specificity that a community expects and, more importantly, could never gather as much trust.

If scattered, specific repositories are unavoidable, how should we then facilitate exchange? To solve this question, we must take inspiration from the other major decentralised structure that forms the backbone of modern day technology: the internet. While online data services are extremely scattered and heterogeneous, they are still able to interact with each other in order to be used together in a single web application through Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). These interfaces allow multiple separate services to be used together through programmatic means by exposing possible interaction points in a pre-described, highly ordered set of functions that can be called by external applications. Applying this to distributed scientific repositories, we can easily think of a model where all these data services adhere to a common, minimal set of API functions that allow them to exchange data with each other. This minimal standard should be governed by an external authority that represents the scientific landscape. Practically, existing governmental agents such as Nationaal Platform Open Science, SURF or the European Union would fulfil this role.

RECOMMENDATIONS

By creating a distributed system with standardised exchange facilities, WUR allows scientific data to be exchanged effortlessly between groups, institutes and companies nationally and internationally. API standards should be published at a centralised point (even a centralised web address would be feasible, e.g. api.wur.nl with separate subdomains) so that they can be harvested and indexed by WUR and other interested parties. Note that publishing APIs publicly does not mean that data is made public; in

The Breeding API (BrAPI) is a large initiative by various crop breeding research partners that standardises the exchange between data on various crop plants. This API is used as the de facto standard for many consortia on crop plants, such as banana, tomato, wheat, oat and many others. It facilitates exchange between many separate, community led data repositories and at the same time standardises the data collection and presentation

fact, using such a standardised interface allows for very fine grained authorisation models. Such a standardised and centralised endpoint for data sharing would greatly improve collaborations with companies. Currently collaboration with companies is often very limited by the lack of this type of interface, as data is either delivered statically limiting its usefulness or the external partner must be given access to WUR internal systems with all associated security risks. Structuring data in a way that facilitates sharing through interfaces is a proven, future proof way to get the most value out of WUR scientific results.

Summarising, WUR should:

- Safeguard the sustainability of existing community repositories within WUR, e.g. through sustainable funding
- Stimulate participation and data deposition in community led repositories
- Require community repositories to expose machine actionable interfaces (APIs) according to standardised specifications, and centrally publish those specifications
- Harvest metadata from community repositories to make WUR wide data search and analytics a possibility

Empower Governance

Data governance is a complex topic because of changing laws and progressive insight into the meaning of data to our work and life. Even defining seemingly simple terms such as 'data ownership' can prove to be an exhausting exercise because of the number of parties involved in the data process. Legally, all data produced by WUR researchers is owned by WUR. If the data represents new, innovative Intellectual Property (IP), another set of rules apply regarding monetisation and patenting. It is not difficult to see why many researchers choose to sidestep these legal quagmires, and instead act on good faith alone. However, data agreements are especially important in collaborations with third parties. Right now, WUR is actively losing collaborative opportunities due to researchers' lack of expertise in making clear decisions around data sharing and ownership.

STARTLIFE Agrifoodtech Accelerator

StartLife empowers founders to build and grow Foodtech & Agtech startups with lasting impact. Since 2010, StartLife has built, supported and funded 300+ startups with hosting communities of investors & experts, developing entrepreneurial competences of startups, offering mentoring programs and providing pre-seed funding and access to capital

To many, even the most simplified ways to settle these legal issues will be seen as a 'ticking the boxes' exercise. However, provided the right tools and information, legal frameworks can empower scientists to realise the value of their data and leverage that value accordingly. While each situation is unique, many questions regarding data ownership, IP, sharing conditions are asked frequently. This means that standardised template

agreements would facilitate answering these questions very well. Modularity of these agreements would allow adaptation to specific situations, allowing parties to select the conditions that apply to the legal relation. Of course, even using standardised agreements legal oversight should always be present. Currently many researchers are not sure where and how to receive legal counsel; a central legal desk, that actively presents itself as approachable is needed to improve this situation. For example, choice of licensing is relevant when publishing open data. Several widely used licenses exist for making data open, ranging from the very permissive MIT license to the iron-clad 'copyleft' licenses of the GPL family. While choice of license is crucial to legally determine what can and cannot be done with data after publishing, many scientists do not feel qualified to make this choice. A legal helpdesk can work together with scientists to help them with these types of questions.

While legal frameworks can be considered 'hard' governance, expectations from scientists, the institute and the public can be qualified as 'soft' governance. While the 'soft' rules are not as clear-cut, ethical considerations are as important as 'hard' rules; breaking them can lead to immense damages in reputation of the institute and even

the position of science in society. The application of novel data-based technologies is currently under heavy scrutiny. The role of Facebook during the 2016 and 2020 US presidential elections, the application of AI driven risk assessment system SyRI by the Dutch government and disinformation promoted by social media feed algorithms are all examples in which data driven applications have far reaching societal consequences. WUR research also has the capacity to affect society deeply: WUR agricultural research is an important influence in the creation of policies by the Dutch government. These same policies have given rise to large scale ongoing farmer protests. It is therefore of the highest importance that WUR has full confidence in the data driven methods it uses to produce research outcomes. This means confidence in the integrity of data used, absence of bias (as much as possible), and assumptions that represent reality as accurately as possible. While researchers in all fields are highly trained experts in dealing with these potential flaws, it is still necessary to reflect *publicly* on their results in light of these factors. This means having scientists discuss their research with those that feel its effects. Examples of this are public conversation events, outreach events presenting WUR results to the world and representation of all stakeholders in ethical boards.

Summarizing, WUR should:

- Let researchers leverage existing legal frameworks to protect and valorise their data with external partners
- Unify existing, group specific approaches to data ownership and sharing agreements into a modular agreement templates for SLA's, Data Sharing Agreements, Confidentiality Agreements, etc.
- Provide legal consulting when applying modular templates through a central legal desk
- Leverage the national cooperation SURF to enforce data sovereignty when using platforms from large, American tech companies.
- Organise events and workshops oriented towards the public, to enable dialogue and societal representation of WUR research.

Machine Actionable

Scientific research is always performed by humans. Even in a future where AI or even more advanced techniques perform most tasks, at some level humans will direct the actions of these machines. The insight, contextual knowledge and creativity needed in scientific research make it most likely to be the last human process to be fully automated, if ever. Therefore we must always put human needs first, when storing and managing data. But while humans excel in finding new creative solutions to problems, they are limited in the amount of information that they can use during this process. The boundaries of the human mind, while flexible and creative, are not enough to hold the amount of data that modern technology is able to produce. Therefore, to maximise the potential of the man-machine interface, machines should be able to provide data at the precise time humans need it and in the right amount. To be able to do this, data needs to be described in such a way, that a machine is able to process the query of a researcher and produce results in the right context. This concept is summarised by a quote from biosemantics professor Barend Mons: 'The machine knows what I mean'.

To understand the meaning of human queries, a wide spectrum of human contexts must be described to a computer. When a PhD student from France searches for "cultures aux Pays-Bas", the computer should be able to determine based on the context of the researcher, whether they are searching for crops most frequently grown in the Netherlands or the various cultural attitudes of Dutch citizens. To solve this problem, semantic technology such as vocabularies and ontologies are unavoidable.

In every field of science, efforts are made to capture definitions, relations and translations of concepts of domain specific terms. Some examples relevant for the domains of WUR are the Agronomy Ontology for agricultural practices, ECOCORE for ecological entities and FoodOn for farm-to-fork concepts of foods around the world. Even though these vocabularies and ontologies are domain specific, their categorical nature makes it possible to map key terms from one ontology to another providing cross domain knowledge networks.

Many data that is now gathered is not enriched with any semantic information. And of the datasets that are enriched, many only contain semantic annotations of a bibliographic nature, such as author, publishing date, etc. While important and useful, these annotations are often of little help in

WECR DATAWAREHOUSE

The datawarehouse at Wageningen Economic Research contains data collected as part of the Statutory Research Tasks (WOT) on economic farming practice in the Netherlands. An enormous collection of animal stock, crop yield, food prices, consumption data and much more. To use this data to its maximum potential data is enriched using universal semantic concepts, meaning a query for "aardappels" will produce the same results as a query for "potatoes". This enables researchers to interact with the data in the way that fits their research question, combining data and performing calculations on the fly.

scientific queries. Semantic annotation also provides a measure of fitness for purpose; precise annotation can play a key role in deciding whether data is fit for re-use by the scientist that finds it. This means semantic annotation is the basis for determining data quality. Data trust and quality are the most important factor for researchers to select data for reuse and so perform an important gatekeeping function. Data that is semantically annotated allows precise selection and quality judgement by other scientists, increasing its re-use. WUR should therefore prioritise annotating data through semantic models, especially in cross domain or large scale data collection projects.

The FAIR (see lower inset) principles provide a high level standard on how to make scientific data machine readable. FAIR does not only improve data quality for scientists directly, it also adds to the growing body of data that can be found to train artificial intelligence models. Because training data for these models must be very carefully selected for purpose and exclusion of bias, FAIR data provides the metadata needed to perform this selection in an automated way, across the entire body published scientific results. Because of this, FAIR is sometimes also expanded as “Fully AI ready”. The upcoming importance of AI in delivering WUR data (see the first chapter on Digital Companion), implies that FAIRifying data is not just adhering to standards but preparing data for the future. Especially when combined with semantic information, FAIR data leads to an interconnected Web of Knowledge that will provide seamless interaction between humans and machines.

Currently the WUR research data policy (<https://www.wur.nl/en/Value-Creation-Cooperation/WDCC/Data-Management-WDCC/Data-policy.htm>) outlines in detail how and when researchers are expected to make their data FAIR. Adoption of this policy in daily research practice is still limited however. Much work on the practical aspects of making data FAIR has already been done by the RDM support team consisting of a mix of FB-IT, library and WDCC staff. This team is greatly assisted by a network of data stewards spread throughout the organisation. This network, consisting of more than 120 data stewards form a direct line of contact with researchers and all the issues they face when performing data management. As the data steward role matures within the organisation, they are expected to start performing more and more duties that are currently part of the RDM support team. This, together with the expanding number of data stewards makes for a powerful cornerstone for further adoption and securing of scientific data standards. Safeguarding and expanding this network should be one of WUR’s top data priorities in the coming years.

Summarising, WUR should:

- Provide FAIR-enabling data infrastructure for every stage of research, from analysis to archive
- Enable data indexability using Persistent Identifiers
- Provide interfaces for machines and applications to interact with WUR data
- Connect researchers to existing standards and standard setting organisations
- Stimulate researchers to use and contribute to domain specific vocabularies and ontologies

Registration & Classification

As producer of valuable data for companies, governmental bodies and society, WUR also has the responsibility to keep this data safe. Not only does this mean that data should be protected technically, but also adhere to all regulatory frameworks that are relevant, such as GDPR, Nagoya protocol, and scientific integrity standards. Also, GDPR implementation has changed since its introduction in 2016 with new updates and judicial decisions, such as the striking down of the US – EU Privacy Shield act in 2020. As data becomes more and more central to public life, regulations about data will keep increasing and changing. This means it is key for any data holder to be vigilant about these changes and to have the means to adjust security and privacy measures when necessary. Challenges around legal agreements, such as NDAs, can also be seen as part of this vigilance.

Besides adhering to regulations, technical security is absolutely essential to uphold in a knowledge institute. Every computer on the internet could, in theory, connect to every other computer on the internet. While most of us understand this on a conceptual level, the implications are often severely underestimated. In the past 10 years information security has had to leap forward to stay ahead of ever more sophisticated adversaries that use online technology to capture data illegitimately. With the advent of ransomware it is not the resell value of stolen data, but the value to the victim that matters. The high-quality scientific data produced by WUR is central to its primary process and is therefore of immense value to the institute. Attackers know this and do not shy away from sophisticated intrusions into systems, taking months to map and judge ideal targets to hold hostage; this exact situation occurred at the University of Maastricht at the end of 2019.

To achieve the appropriate level of regulation & security standards, WUR should strive for two goals for all its data:

- Centralised registration of data
- Classification of data, based on impact

Challenges in implementing appropriate information security policies are the fast changing nature of the outside world, as well as finding a balance between usability and security. Because of these rapid accelerating insights and nuances, implementing security is best left to specialists. Their expertise allows a balance to be struck between the levels of restrictions that are put on datasets vs. their usability and openness. Another important balancing factor are the costs of implementing high effort security measures. These considerations, together with the practicality that not all data needs to be protected at the highest level can be used to provide policies that strike a perfect balance between security, usability and expenses.

To enable a perfectly balanced security model for all data within WUR, security specialists must be able to judge data for its value. This is accomplished using a classification model that considers the impact of various scenarios. It consists of 4 levels describing the scale of this impact, cross referenced with four domains of Operational, Privacy, Financial and Reputation. See the table below for clarification.

IMPACT	REPUTATION	OPERATIONAL	FINANCIAL	PRIVACY
NEGLIGIBLE	Very little publication in media (local or social)	No or very little interruption to research / education	Costs or penalty €0-€25.000	Exposure of non-sensitive personal data <100 individuals
SOME	Some negative publication in local or social media	Some interruption of research / education	Costs or penalty €25.000-€250.000	Exposure of contextually sensitive data <100 individuals
SERIOUS	Negative publication in national media	Long term disruption of education / research	Costs or penalty €250.000-€2,5m	Exposure of data for >1000 individuals Exposure of sensitive data for >100 individuals
DISRUPTIVE	Long term negative publication in media Societal protest, digitally and physically	Large scale institutional disruption of education / research Security threat for employees / students	Costs or penalty >€2,5m	Exposure of sensitive data for >10.000 individuals Safety threat for data subjects

Using this model, data is classified according to the highest impact on any four of these domains. While the model is simple enough for a layperson to fill in, it provides enough nuance to appropriately secure data using institutional infrastructure. It allows security specialists to make the right decisions to ensure the availability, integrity and confidentiality of data.

Summarising, WUR should:

- Promote and educate users on the registration & classification of research data
- Facilitate registration & classification of research data in all research data management infrastructure
- Monitor compliance of data classification at an institutional, and research unit level and draft consequences for non-compliance.

Infrastructure Accessibility

Statistical analysis is ubiquitous in scientific analysis. As the application of statistical models become more and more complex, so do the computational requirements. In every scientist's career, there comes a moment where the analysis outgrows the laptop they are working on. This problem does not only occur with classical statistics: all kinds of modelling analysis, from MCMC to neural networks, usually require significant computational time. Several solutions exist, one of which is simply waiting a long time for completion. This solution can be found walking through the WUR corridors today: desktop or laptop pc's with a sticky note on them saying "DO NOT TURN OFF!". While extremely simple and accessible, this solution leaves something to be desired. It is fragile (hence the sticky notes) and it takes up expensive researcher hours. Especially because analyses are often iterative: upon completion it often requires running again with slightly improved parameters, or with the next in a series of datasets.

Another solution is buying a faster computer. This is also done regularly in many research groups, and is often combined with the sticky-note solution. However, computational time tends to grow exponentially as datasets and parameter spaces increase, so this solution usually only provides temporary relief. It also becomes a liability, because now (expensive) research data is taken outside of WUR-serviced hardware and depends on local enthusiast support, often neglecting security, continuity and integrity standards. Incidents such as data unavailability or loss interrupt the scientific process, delaying progress towards breakthroughs. At an organisational level, it also means researchers spend many hours on data 'wrangling': the error-prone process of dragging data around and converting it to the various formats needed.

Lastly there is outsourcing the analysis to external hardware. WUR has its own High Performance Cluster, which facilitates large scale computing combined with high-throughput data storage. NWO funded researchers also have free access to Snellius, the national supercomputer which allows even larger scale up scenarios. These communal infrastructures provide safe, stable computation and are often supported by a large community of researchers. This makes them a much better alternative than the two self-managed solutions mentioned before.

Outsourcing computation presents three major hurdles however: technical compatibility, administrative load and financial demands. Because high-performance clusters

JUPYTER NOTEBOOKS

The Jupyter Notebook is an open-source web application that allows you to create and share documents that contain live code, equations, visualizations and narrative text. It allows students and researchers to create and tune complex modelling code in many different programming languages in an interactive manner. At WUR, it is used as a visual frontend for the HPC to facilitate large scale analysis through an environment that is familiar to the user.

are big, but not endless, compute hours still cost money. Compared to researcher-hours, these costs are usually fractional but they can be unsurmountable if they are not accounted for in project budgets. Because of a lack of experience and / or the unpredictability of the scientific process, these costs often come as a nasty surprise during a project. Additionally, clusters require some on-boarding knowledge to convert analysis from a personal workstation to the queue driven system of the HPC. While no in-depth knowledge of HPC inner workings is necessary, some command-line instructions are needed to manage computation jobs. Finally, the administrative load of registering an account and managing compute hours add to an already mounting pile of paperwork that, while important, interferes with daily research activities.

These hurdles lead to many scientists avoiding large communal infrastructures. Where the above example presents the case for computation, the same hurdles appear for many infrastructures: versioning code by emailing it to yourself vs. using Gitlab, emailing manuscripts around vs. using a collaborative LaTeX platform, external hard-drives instead of network storage, etc. This underutilisation of communal infrastructures leads to defunding, further undermining their appeal. The solution to this is threefold: educating users, lowering thresholds and investing in common infrastructures to make them more attractive.

Educating users can be done in the form of on- or offline courses. Recordings and offline manuals can allow researchers to learn at their own pace. Part of education is also outreach oriented towards new users. Many users are not familiar with every piece of technology out there and are therefore not aware what it can do to solve their problems. Advanced courses can help developers get more out of technology and, coupled with communities, this can lead to a thriving data driven research ecosystem.

Administrative burdens are correlated with financial ones, and reducing the latter usually eliminate (or at least reduce) the former. Therefore, communal infrastructure should always be *at least free-to-start*. Free-to-start means that a researcher is able to use the service without any budget, up to a limit that is reasonable to find out if the service is able to solve their problem. In a perfect world, common infrastructures would be completely free without any limits. However this soon leads to a tragedy of the commons, where a minority of users occupy the majority of the capacity exhausting the service for others. Therefore, at least a fair use limitation is usually appropriate. Free-to-start also means the service must be somewhat actively monitored to regularly prune non-active users who might be exhausting resources. The benefits of this model far outweigh the costs of this minimal required monitoring. It allows users, developers and innovators to use infrastructure freely and, more importantly, allows them to work with technology creatively to achieve scientific breakthroughs. Lowering the barriers to technology is one of the easiest yet most effective ways to advance the data driven ambitions of WUR going into the new decade.

Lastly, there is the question of locality. Should WUR keep investing in local hardware and development of services as cloud adoption is growing on all fronts? The answer is twofold: Local infrastructure *increases* accessibility by being the focal point in a network of human users and developers. This ecosystem stimulates, educates and supports new users in using the facility. The other benefit of local infrastructure is independency. While current offerings from large cloud suppliers are very supportive of research, they also focus on serving the large majority of users. Research often has exotic and

innovative needs which is optimally developed in short feedback cycles and in close collaboration with the provider. Therefore, local expertise is essential in serving research development. While commercial cloud offerings offer many advantages, they should always be supported by a group of supporters that are easily reachable by the researcher and who, ideally, co-create solutions with the researcher.

Summarizing, WUR should:

- Organise courses for all common infrastructures oriented for different user levels and maintaining current ones
- Make all common research infrastructures free-to-start, lowering barriers to entry and application
- Invest in local platforms, such as HPC and research data management systems, to create thriving social and technical ecosystems.

From recommendation to implementation

In this document, a number of recommendations are made to enhance WUR data handling and infrastructure for the coming years. How should these recommendations be put into action? A strategic document focuses on the what and why, not the how. In this final section, we present possible directions for getting to the how, through current and new to start activities.

DATA STRATEGY AS A BACKBONE FOR WDCC PROGRAMME EXECUTION

The directions laid out in this document are fully supported by the observations and use cases managed by WDCC. While these use cases form practical applications of the WUR vision on data science and data management, large shifts are taking place in the digital landscape. A growing number of scientific groups are recognising this and are reorienting themselves towards a new scientific landscape. Often, they seek out WDCC to provide insight and experience during this process. With this data strategy, WDCC will have a clear, acknowledged vision of trends and strategies that these parties can use to start their own transformation towards data driven science. This also makes sure that realigning priorities are performed from the same starting point across WUR.

CURRENTLY STRATEGIC MOVEMENTS

In the below figure an overview is presented of the strategic recommendations made in this document and the level of maturity WUR has towards achieving this goal.

Strategic Goal Maturity & Activities

Unrecognised	Interested	Invested	Committed	Engaged	Embedded
<i>No awareness or efforts towards goal</i>	<i>Awareness, but no efforts towards goal</i>	<i>Goal is recognised, effort has begun</i>	<i>Organisational commitment towards achieving goal</i>	<i>Goal is standard practice in parts of the organisation</i>	<i>Goal is standard practice in the whole organisation</i>

- with suggested new programmes -

Strategic goals, and their maturity within the organisation. In red are suggested new investments to further activities towards goals.

Digital companion: lower maturity, but high need from the organisation

Digital companion is a novel concept, and its practical application in the organisation still requires a number of steps to be taken. At the same time, WDCC receives many higher level questions that could be solved with a Digital companion approach. Many research groups have a steadily growing collection of high quality data, models and associated insights that they would like to share in a platform setting rather than through a collection of papers and reports. They also see *themselves* as a main user of this platform, reusing their own data to provide additional value for their new experiments. WDCC therefore recommends to centralise approaches to create these types of platforms, by providing standards and digital infrastructure; see the 'Strategic Investments' section at the end of this chapter.

Empowering governance through better data sharing guidelines

As part of the establishment of data sharing guidelines, work is ongoing to assist in the empowerment of data sharing through legal means. The outcomes of this work are gathered under the data support pages at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/Value-Creation-Cooperation/Collaborating-with-WUR-1/WDCC/Data-Management-WDCC/Data-policy/Data-Sharing-guidelines.htm>. One of these is a Data Sharing Agreement Framework, which gives a starting point for what agreements must be made between parties when sharing data.

New & accessible infrastructure through Domein regie team research

In December 2020, a new organisational structure was ratified in the WUR information management domain. A domein regie team (domain strategic team, DRT) was formed spearheaded by the Dean of Research, head of Information Management, head of FB-IT and Director of WDCC. This new organisational component has the explicit goal to establish and improve common WUR research infrastructures in such a way that they are beneficial and accessible for all WUR researchers. This directly strengthens the 'Accessible infrastructure' goal. Through this goal, WUR will be able to provide a portfolio of services that benefit all researchers, eliminating double work and maximising effective use of researcher time and resources.

Serious about data – security / classification

As part of the new information security policy, WUR is investing in the accelerated implementation of this policy. This does not only entail improvements on the technology side, but also awareness and co-creation activities to improve security measures in existing research and education solutions. An example of this is the 'WUR is serious about data' programme, which coordinates awareness and implementation activities around data privacy and security.

WDCC RDM, Yoda / iRODS – Distribute & standardise

WDCC activities in general are already aligned with the strategic goals mentioned in this document, but specifically towards data distribution and standardisation, researchers are supported in two ways. One is the Yoda programme, which is a collaborative effort between most universities in the Netherlands and SURF to provide the Yoda data platform as a daily driver RDM solution for all users. The other is the application of iRODS middleware to unify existing infrastructure into bespoke solutions for complex data projects, such as the NPEC project.

POSSIBLE STRATEGIC INVESTMENTS

Finally, we recommend three new programmes to be started to further the high level goals posed in this strategy (also highlighted in red in the overview figure).

Centralised support for data delivery platforms and Digital Companion initiatives

WDCC has produced a handbook for scientists to aid in developing Digital Companion initiatives in a financially sustainable way. This handbook is the first step in a larger programme to assist in the various aspects that underlie the feasibility of a digital companion platform in terms of infrastructure, maintainability and value. Part of this programme will be the development of standardised legal, advisory and ICT services to assist researchers and research groups in creating these platforms.

WDCC expects this programme to fill a need heard in many groups, either by providing them with needed infrastructure or advising them how to create a digital companion on their own terms. In addition, this programme will provide guidance for investment decisions towards existing data delivery platforms.

Towards the data driven lab

The wet lab is one of the most prolific sources of digital data at WUR. From large, production labs such as WFSR to the smaller experimental labs, they all produce significant amounts of data that need to be managed. Specific products exist to facilitate this, such as electronic lab journals, lab inventory management systems, and vendor specific equipment centric software. However, in many labs the flow of data between these systems is an error prone, manual process. It also leaves much data isolated on specific lab pc's which are hard to access without being physically in the lab, a problem which became much more urgent during the COVID related work from home restrictions. Lab pc's are also often not part of a good backup regime, producing integrity and availability risks for valuable research data.

To concretise the 'Machine Actionable' as well as the 'Distribute and Standardise' goals, WDCC recommends to start a Information Management led program to provide a standardised blueprint for a data driven lab. This should result in a high-level overview of standard lab processes and their data flows. Accompanying this architecture the FB-IT portfolio should be synchronised to support all generic parts in this blueprint.

Research Compute & AI lab

Research IT solutions usually have complex needs. A variety of more standard IT services such as HPC, storage, cloud, and more dedicated PaaS or SaaS services are usually needed in a combined solution. At the moment, IT services are distributed across various teams which makes it difficult to realise combined solutions utilising multiple services from separate teams. Recognising this situation, TU/e has initiated an 'HPC lab' where research engineers create complex solutions based on research use cases, often working with researchers directly. Many of the research engineers have a research background themselves, making the interface between them and users easier. For TU/e this has proven to be a very successful model, implementing many use cases and distilling new standard services from the custom solutions built. A similar setup would work very well for the complex use cases at WUR; starting a project for the creation of a similar, lab-style approach for digital research solutions is the last recommended investment.